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Multi-Feature, Multi-Classifer Analysis in EMG Diagnosis

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Abstract

In the case of difficult pattern recognition problems, the combination of the outputs of multiple classifiers using for input multiple feature sets extracted from the raw data, can improve the overall classification performance. In this work a modular neural network system in EMG diagnosis is presented where multiple features extracted from the motor unit action potential (MUAP) waveforms recorded during routine electromyographic (EMG) examination were fed into multiple classifiers, and the classification results were combined in order to improve the diagnostic yield. The feature sets computed, were: (i) the time domain parameters, (ii) the frequency domain parameters, (iii) the autoregressive coefficients, (iv) the cepstral coefficients and (v) the wavelet transform coefficients for four different wavelets (Daubechies with 4 and 20 coefficients, Chui, and Battle-Lemarie). The classifiers implemented were: (i) the back-propagation (BP), (ii) the radial basis function (RBF) network and (iii) the self-organising feature map (SOFM). The proposed system was developed for the assessment of normal subjects and subjects suffering with myopathy and motor neuron disease. It was shown that the modular neural network system enhanced the diagnostic performance of the individual classifiers making the whole system more robust and reliable.

1 INTRODUCTION

The diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders is a naturally complex and difficult problem to investigate. This group of disorders affects the brain and spinal cord, nerves, or muscles. Their main characteristic is muscular weakness and/or wasting, with the life expectancy of many sufferers being considerably reduced. Early detection and diagnosis of these diseases by laboratory tests and neurophysiological examinations, like EMG are essential for their prognosis, management, and prevention. The shapes of motor unit action potentials (MUAPs) composing the electromyographic (EMG) signal, provide an important source of information for the assessment of neuromuscular disorders. In computer aided EMG the MUAP waveforms derived by quantitative EMG techniques [1], and their computed parameters are presented to the physician in order to assist him in the assessment of the disease and subsequently in reaching a final diagnosis. A computerised decision support system which will automatically evaluate all of the above given data in a consistent and uniform manner allowing a standardized, more accurate, and less time-consuming assessment of EMG findings, and which will give the physician a second, unbiased opinion will provide an important aid in the current practice of clinical neurophysiology.

The development of decision support systems based on artificial neural networks (ANN) has shown promising results in different areas of medical applications [2]. The motivation behind the use of ANN lies in their capacity for making no assumptions about the underlying probability density functions, finding near-optimum solutions from incomplete data sets, and the fact that learning is accomplished through training. In addition to these characteristics, neural networks can combine data of a different nature in one system, such as data derived from clinical protocols and laboratory data obtained from measurements and features from signals and images, thus forming an integrated diagnostic system [3], [4].

The performance of ANN models can be further enhanced by the development of modular neural networks, where the outputs of different modular neural modules are combined in order to form the final output of the system. Modular neural networks easily allow the combined use of supervised and unsupervised learning paradigms or different learning algorithms. This combines the advantages of the individual modules and can improve the overall performance. More specifically, in the case of difficult pattern recognition problems, the combination of the outputs of multiple classifiers using for input multiple feature sets extracted from the raw

data, can substantially improve the overall classification performance. In the case of noisy or of a limited amount of data, different classifiers often provide different generalisations by realising different decision boundaries. Also, different feature sets provide different representations of the input patterns, containing different classification information. Selecting the best classifier or the best feature set is not necessarily the ideal choice, since potentially valuable information contained in the less successful feature sets or classifiers may be lost. The combination of the results of the different features and the different classifiers increases the probability that the errors of the individual features or classifiers may be compensated by the correct results of the rest [5].

The objective of this study is to investigate the usefulness of modular neural networks in the development of a multi-feature, multi-classifier diagnostic system for neuromuscular disorders based on electromyographic findings.

2 MATERIAL

In this study, EMG was recorded from the biceps brachii muscle at a slight voluntary contraction for 5 seconds using the concentric needle electrode. The signal was then bandpass filtered at 3 Hz to 10 kHz, and sampled at 20 kHz with 12 bits resolution. The signal was then lowpass filtered at 10 kHz. MUAP waveforms with similar shape were identified and selected from the EMG recording using an unsupervised learning neural network system [6]. Similar MUAPs were averaged to obtain the averaged MUAP waveform, which is thereafter simply referred to as MUAP. The MUAP epoch consisted of 512 samples (25.6 ms).

A total of 800 MUAPs were recorded from 40 subjects, 12 normal (NOR), 13 suffering with myopathy (MYO) and 15 suffering with motor neuron disease (MND). Diagnostic criteria were based on clinical opinion, biochemical data and muscle biopsy. Only subjects with no history or signs of neuromuscular disorders were considered as normal. The modular neural network system was trained and tested for the three classes. Different sets with eight subjects from each group were randomly selected to form the ANN training set, whereas the remaining subjects formed the ANN evaluation set.

3 MULTI-FEATURE, MULTI-CLASSIFIER ANALYSIS

The combination of eight different feature sets extracted from the MUAP waveforms as described below and three different neural network classifiers were investigated for the classification of EMG signals into a disease class (see Fig. 1). For each subject the average vector of 20 MUAPs per subject for each feature set was computed and used as input to the classifiers. The classification results of the different feature sets and the different classifiers were combined using majority voting in order to improve the diagnostic yield.

3.1 Multiple Features

For each subject a matrix of 20 MUAP waveforms x 512 samples, was available for further processing. From each MUAP waveform the following feature sets were extracted:

(i) Time domain parameters. Time domain parameters are the most widely used parameters in clinical neurophysiology for the interpretation of EMG findings. The following time domain parameters were computed from the MUAP waveforms [7]: duration, spike duration, amplitude, area, spike area, number of phases and number of turns.

(ii) Frequency domain parameters. The following frequency domain parameters were computed from the MUAP waveforms: spectral moments of order 0, 1 and 2 (M_0 , M_1 , and M_2), median frequency and quality factor. Spectral moments M_1 and M_2 represent the area of the power spectrum after being weighted by frequency raised to the power of one and two respectively. The time domain and the frequency domain parameters were further normalised by division with their mean values.

(iii) Autoregressive coefficients. In the autoregressive model a current signal $x(n)$ is described as linear combination of previous samples $x(n-k)$ weighted by a coefficient [8]. The autoregressive (AR) model order p and the coefficients α_1 to α_{12} were computed from the MUAP signal.

(iv) Cepstral coefficients. The cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} were computed from the AR coefficients. The motivation for using the cepstral coefficients is their high discrimination ability documented in speech recognition compared to the AR coefficients [9].

(v) **Wavelet coefficients.** The wavelet transform (WT) provides a linear two dimensional time-frequency representation and was investigated for describing MUAP morphology. The WT was investigated because it has the ability to localize the changes in the statistics of nonstationary signals and it provides an alternative to the classical Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) which uses a single analysis window [10]. The WT uses short windows at high frequencies and long windows at low frequencies. Four different wavelets were computed: Daubechies 4 (*DAU4* **Error! Switch argument not specified.**) and 20 (*DAU20* **Error! Switch argument not specified.**) with 4 and 20 coefficients respectively, Chui (*CH* **Error! Switch argument not specified.**) and Battle-Lemarie (*BL* **Error! Switch argument not specified.**) [11].

3.2 Multiple Classifiers

In this work both supervised and unsupervised learning techniques were used for training the ANN models. The three classifiers were implemented using the following algorithms:

(i) **Back-propagation algorithm.** The supervised learning error back-propagation (BP) algorithm [12] with momentum and adaptive learning rate was used for training a three layer feedforward network. Momentum prevents the network from getting trapped at a shallow local minimum of the error surface, leading to a failure to converge and subsequently in reaching a global minimum. Momentum is added by making weight changes $\Delta w(t+1)$ equal to the sum of a fraction of the last weight change $\Delta w(t)$ and the new change derived by the BP algorithm. The BP algorithm with momentum is expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\Delta w(t+1) = m \Delta w(t) + (1 - m) x \eta \delta \quad (1)$$

where m is the momentum constant set typically to 0.95, x are the input values, η the learning rate and δ is the error signal given by the BP algorithm. Also, in order to speed up learning, an adaptive learning rate η can be used. If the new error exceeds the old error by more than a predefined ratio, no weight change takes place and the learning rate decreases. If the error is less, then the learning rate is increased.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of the multi-feature, multi-classifier EMG diagnostic system: the average of the features extracted from the MUAPs per subject are used as input to the BP, RBF and SOFM classifiers. The outputs of the three classifiers are combined using majority voting.

(ii) **Radial-basis function network.** The radial-basis function (RBF) network was used for supervised learning [13]. The network was trained using an incremental solver, adding iteratively one neuron per epoch until a preset sum squared error goal is met or the maximum number of neurons is reached. The output of each neuron is given by

$$y = RBF(\|x-w\| / Sp) \quad (2)$$

where RBF is a Gaussian function, $\|x-w\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the input vector x and the weight vector w and Sp is the spread parameter. The output increases as the distance between the input and weight vectors decreases. The spread parameter should be large enough so that the RBF neurons respond to overlapping regions of the input space but not so large that all the neurons respond in essentially the same manner.

(iii) **Self-Organising feature map algorithm.** The self-organising feature map (SOFM) algorithm is an unsupervised learning algorithm where the input patterns are freely distributed over the output node matrix [14]. The weights are adapted without supervision in such a way, so that the density distribution of the input data is preserved and represented on the output nodes. This mapping of similar input patterns to output nodes which are close to each other represents a discretisation of the input space, allowing a visualization of the distribution of the input data. The output nodes are usually ordered in a two dimensional grid, and the weights of the output nodes in the neighborhood of the winning output node are adapted simultaneously. The neighborhood around the winning output node, decreases in size over time. The weights of the output nodes in the neighborhood are adapted with

$$w(t+1) = w(t) + \eta h(t) (x - w(t)) \quad (3)$$

where η is the learning rate ($0 < \eta \leq 1$) and $h(t)$ is a decreasing function which decreases with time. At the end of the training phase, the output nodes were labelled with the class of the majority of the input patterns of the training set, assigned to each node. In the evaluation phase, an input pattern was assigned to the output node with the weight vector closest to the input vector, and it was said to belong to the class label of the winning output node where it had been assigned.

3.3 Classification results combining

The classification results of the three classifiers were combined in three different ways, using simple majority voting in order to improve the diagnostic yield:

(i) **Combining the outputs for the eight different feature sets for each classifier.** The eight different feature sets were applied to the BP, RBF and SOFM classifiers. Each feature set applied to a classifier yielded an output, indicating whether the specific subject belongs to the NOR, or MYO or MND group. The eight outputs corresponding to the eight feature sets of each classifier were combined using majority voting. The subject was assigned to the class with the maximum votes.

(ii) **Combining the results of the three classifiers.** As described above, the combination of the eight feature sets by each classifier yielded an output result. The three output results of the three classifiers were further combined using majority voting.

(iii) **Combining the outputs derived from the eight different feature sets from the three classifiers.** The 24 output results of the eight feature sets applied to the three classifiers were combined using majority voting. The highest diagnostic yield was obtained by the combination of the 24 classification results of all feature sets from all classifiers.

4 RESULTS

A total of 480 MUAPs obtained from 24 subjects, 8 NOR, 8 MYO and 8 MND, were used for training the ANN classifiers, whereas a total of 320 MUAPs, obtained from 16 subjects, 4 NOR, 5 MYO and 7 MND were used for evaluation. Due to the rather limited amount of the input data and in order to verify the correctness of the classification results a bootstrapping procedure was used. The system was trained and evaluated using five different bootstrap sets where in each set 24 different subjects were selected at random for training and 16 different subjects for evaluation. The mean percentage and the standard deviation (Std) of the correct classifications score, i.e. diagnostic yield, for the five bootstrap sets was computed for each classifier, for the eight different feature sets. Table I tabulates the mean and Std of the diagnostic yield of the modular neural network EMG diagnostic system for the five sets. The classification results are given for each feature set per classifier and the results by the combination of features and classifiers.

Table I Mean and standard deviation of the diagnostic yield (DY%) for the evaluation set of the multi-feature, multi-classifier EMG diagnostic system, illustrated in Fig. 1 after bootstrapping the available data for five different sets of subjects. The average feature vector for each subject for eight different feature sets were fed to three different classifiers, and their results were combined.

<i>Feature set</i>	<i>n</i> ¹	<i>BP</i> <i>DY%</i>	<i>RBF</i> <i>DY%</i>	<i>SOFM</i> <i>DY%</i>	<i>Average</i> <i>DY%</i>	<i>Combiners</i> <i>DY%</i>
Time domain	7	81.2 ± 11.8	72.5 ± 8.5	81.2 ± 5.5	78.3 ± 8.6	
Frequency domain	5	63.7 ± 2.5	60.0 ± 6.3	63.7 ± 10.1	62.5 ± 6.3	
Autoregressive	12	56.2 ± 7.9	50.0 ± 6.8	47.5 ± 10.1	51.2 ± 8.3	
Cepstral	12	62.5 ± 15.8	60.0 ± 5.0	68.7 ± 3.9	63.7 ± 8.2	
Wavelet <i>DAU4</i>	16	68.7 ± 5.5	60.0 ± 5.0	70.0 ± 6.1	66.2 ± 5.5	
Wavelet <i>DAU20</i>	16	57.5 ± 8.3	55.0 ± 4.6	66.2 ± 6.3	59.6 ± 6.4	
Wavelet <i>CH</i>	16	65.0 ± 6.3	56.2 ± 11.8	68.7 ± 3.9	63.3 ± 7.3	
Wavelet <i>BL</i>	16	65.0 ± 10.1	66.2 ± 8.5	66.2 ± 5.0	65.8 ± 7.9	
<i>Average</i>		65.0 ± 8.5	60.0 ± 7.1	66.5 ± 6.4	63.8 ± 7.3	
<i>Combine features</i> ²		73.7 ± 7.2	72.5 ± 5.0	78.7 ± 6.3	75.0 ± 6.2	
<i>Combine classifiers</i> ³						80.0 ± 6.1
<i>Combine all features from all classifiers</i> ⁴						82.5 ± 4.6

¹ Feature set vector size.

^{2,3,4} See section 3.3, (i), (ii), and (iii) respectively.

For each feature set the average diagnostic yield for the BP, RBF, and SOFM classifiers were computed. The best feature set was the time domain parameters with average diagnostic yield 78.3%, followed by the wavelet transform coefficients *DAU4* with 66.2%, and the *BL* with 65.8%. For each classifier, the average diagnostic yield was computed for all eight feature sets. The best classifier in average was the SOFM with 66.5%, followed closely by the BP classifier with 65.0% and the RBF classifier with 60.0%. The combination of the classification results of the multiple features per classifier, enhanced the diagnostic yield and exceeded significantly the average results achieved by each classifier. For the SOFM classifier, the diagnostic yield by the combination of all feature sets was 78.7% compared to 66.5% for the average yield, for the BP classifier 73.7% compared to 65.0%, and for the RBF classifier 72.5% compared to 60.0%. The combination of the combined results of the three classifiers improved the diagnostic yield further to 80.0%. The best diagnostic yield was achieved by the combination of the 24 classification results of all feature sets from all classifiers and it was 82.5%. This diagnostic yield was higher than the diagnostic yield of the best feature set from the best classifiers, which was 81.2% for the time domain parameters and the SOFM and BP classifiers.

The ANN classifiers were implemented using the BP, the RBF and the SOFM algorithms as they were given in the MATLAB neural networks toolbox [15]. For the BP several network architectures were tested. In general, an architecture which gave good results for the BP algorithm was the one with 40 neurons in the first hidden layer and 20 neurons in the second hidden layer. The RBF algorithm required 22 neurons for learning the input patterns at a sum squared error goal set to 0.02. The spread parameter *Sp* was varied depending on the feature set in order to achieve the best possible performance. For the SOFM algorithm a 5x5 output node matrix was used. The BP classifier was trained for 5000 learning epochs whereas the RBF algorithm converged very fast requiring only 22 learning epochs. The SOFM algorithm was trained for 1000 learning epochs and in general it was faster than the BP algorithm and slower than the RBF algorithm. In every learning epoch all the 24 subjects of the training set were presented to the networks.

5 DISCUSSION

In this paper we have presented how the combination of multiple features and multiple neural network classifiers can be used in order to improve the classification performance of individual features or classifiers. This results a diagnostic system which combines different features sets and different classifiers to be more robust and reliable.

The highest diagnostic yield was obtained by the time domain parameters followed by the wavelet coefficients *DAU4* and *BL*. The better results obtained by the time domain parameters can be justified by the relative simple shape of the EMG signal at low to moderate force levels. At these force levels the time domain parameters can capture most of the information characterising the MUAP waveform. Best classifier was the SOFM followed by the BP. As shown in this study, the use of the unsupervised SOFM algorithm can give better results in cases where there is a high degree of overlap among the classes of the input data. The combination of all features from all classifiers exceeded the diagnostic yield obtained by the best feature with the best classifier.

In this study, the strategy followed for the combination of the neural network outputs was simple majority voting. This linear combination strategy may be expanded by the use of a gating network [16], where the best feature sets and the more successful classifiers will be given a greater weight in the combination of the outputs. The gating network will be trained simultaneously with the other ANN classifiers and will serve as mediator among the classifiers. The gating network will decide based on the input pattern presented which features or classifiers should be given the greater weight in order to achieve the best performance.

In conclusion the results in this work show that modular neural networks are a promising tool in solving difficult pattern recognition problems. The diagnostic results could be verified further using more data from more subjects, both for training and evaluating the system. Finally, the proposed methodology, followed in our work can be applied for the development of modular neural network decision support systems in biosignal analysis in other domains in medicine.

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